

RESULT 3 - TRAINING EVENTS

To access the documentation related to the justification of the results obtained in relation to *ACTIVITY 3: ENTRENEET youth training*, please click on the following links:

[Result 3 - Training Events](#)

[Task 1 - In person community events \(trainings\)](#)

[Task 2 - Webinar content development](#)

[Task 3 - Webinar delivery \(training\)](#)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them. [Project Code: 2022-3-ES02-KA210-YOU-000093384]